

Extractive Spectrophotometric Determination of Cobalt as a Mixed Thiocyanate-Promethazine Complex

P. G. RAMAPPA, H. SANKE GOWDA and S. MANJAPPA

Department of Post-graduate Studies and Research in Chemistry, University of
Mysore, Manasagangotri, Mysore-570 006, India

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A new spectrophotometric method for the determination of traces of cobalt based on the extraction of blue cobalt-thiocyanate-promethazine ion-association complex into chloroform from 1.5-4.5M sulphuric acid medium is described. Beer's law is valid over the concentration range 0.5-45 ppm of cobalt(II). The complex which is stable for over a week has an absorption maximum at 618-616 nm and its molar absorptivity is $1.39 \times 10^3 \text{ l mole}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Many common ions do not interfere. The proposed method offers higher sensitivity than that of the classical reaction with thiocyanate and can be used in media of wider range of acidity and no problems arise from instability.

SANKEGOWDA *et al.*¹ proposed promethazine hydrochloride (PH) as redox indicator for vanadometry. Cavatorta² employed the reaction of palladous chloride with PH for the colorimetric determination of the latter. This paper deals with the extraction of cobalt-thiocyanate with PH in chloroform and its subsequent spectrophotometric determination in the organic phase.

Experimental

Apparatus :

Beckman Model 'DB' spectrophotometer with matched 10 mm quartz cells was used for absorbance measurements. A pH meter Model LI-10 (ELICO, Hyderabad) was used for determining pH of the aqueous phase.

Reagents :

Standard cobalt (II) solution : A stock solution of cobalt (II) was prepared by dissolving cobalt (II) sulphate heptahydrate (AnalaR) in doubly distilled water and was standardised complexometrically³. The working solutions were made by suitable dilution of this stock solution.

PH solution. 0.1M solution of PH in AnalaR chloroform was prepared.

2M aqueous solution of ammonium thiocyanate was prepared.

Diverse ions. Solutions of diverse ions of suitable concentrations were prepared using analytical grade reagents.

Procedure : Place the sample solution containing

56 to 440 μg of cobalt (II) in a separatory funnel. Add 4 ml of 10M sulphuric acid, 5 ml of 2M ammonium thiocyanate and distilled water to bring the total volume to about 20ml. Add 5 ml of 0.1M PH in chloroform and shake for 1 min. Transfer the blue coloured chloroform layer to a 10 ml volumetric flask. Extract the aqueous solution twice with 2 ml portions of chloroform. Combine the chloroform extracts in the same 10 ml volumetric flask and dilute to the mark with chloroform. Measure the absorbance at 622 nm against a reagent blank prepared in the same way. Calculate the cobalt concentration of the sample solution by means of a calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

PH forms an intensely blue ion-association complex with the binary cobalt-thiocyanate complex in 1.5-4.5M sulphuric acid solution. The ion-association complex can be extracted into chloroform while the binary cobalt-thiocyanate complex cannot be extracted under the experimental conditions. The conditional extraction constant of the ternary complex was determined by the modified method of isomolar series⁴. The mean value of $\log K_E'$ was 4.68 ± 0.05 , indicating good extraction with chloroform. The chloroform extract of the cobalt-thiocyanate-PH ion-association complex has an absorption maximum at 618-626 nm (Fig. 1). The reagent blank in chloroform does not show any absorption in the region 500-700 nm. Hence all absorbance measurements were made at 622 nm.

The effects of concentration of mineral acids, ammonium thiocyanate and PH were studied. The absorbance remained constant in 20 ml of 1.5-4.5M sulphuric or hydrochloric acid solution containing 2.5-10 ml of 2M ammonium thiocyanate and 3-8 ml

Fig 1. Absorption spectra of A PH, B Co(II)-SCN complex, and C: Co(II)-SCN-PH complex $[PH]=0.05M$, $[Co]=25$ ppm.

of 0.1M PH in chloroform. Hence the optimum concentration of 2M H_2SO_4 or HCl, 5 ml of 2M ammonium thiocyanate and 5 ml of 0.1M PH in chloroform were selected for the determination of cobalt.

Range and sensitivity : Beer's law was obeyed in the range 0.5-45 ppm, with an optimum working range of 5.6-44 ppm of cobalt. The molar absorptivity was 1.39×10^5 l. mole⁻¹cm⁻¹ and the Sandell sensitivity was 42 ng of Co cm⁻². The sensitivity of the proposed method is higher than that of thiocyanate⁵, pyrazoline derivatives⁶, thiocyanate-1-phenyl-4-phenylamino-1, 2, 4-triazolium chloride⁷ and thiocyanate-tetraphenyl arsonium salts⁸. The absorbance readings remained constant for over one week and were insensitive to temperature in the range 5-45°.

Effect of diverse ions : Several cations and anions were examined by applying the method to fixed amounts of cobalt in the presence of increasing quantities of the ions being studied. The tolerance limits for various diverse ions (Table 1) represent the concentration of foreign ions in the presence of which the absorbance of cobalt-thiocyanate-PH complex solution obtained was within $\pm 2\%$ of the expected value.

Composition of the complex : The ratio of cobalt to thiocyanate and PH was determined by Job's method of continuous variations⁹. Since three components are involved in the formation of the extractable complex, two series of experiments were carried out by keeping one constant and varying the other constituent. The result obtained indicated that the mole ratio of Co(II) to SCN⁻ is 1 : 3 and of Co(II) to PH is 1 : 1. The mole ratio method¹⁰ confirms the ratio of Co(II) to PH as 1 : 1.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS ON THE DETERMINATION OF COBALT (Amount of cobalt taken = 15 ppm)

Ion added	Tolerance limit (ppm)	Ion added	Tolerance limit (ppm)
Na(I)	6000	Ce(IV)	65
K(I)	6000	Ti(IV)	40
Ca(II)	6000	V(V)	500
Mg(II)	6000	Pd(II)	250
Ba(II)	6000	Rh(III)	500
Zn(II)	500	Ir(III)	400
Cd(II)	6000	Ru(III)	2
Pb(II)	6000	Pt(IV)	600
Al(III)	4000	Os(VIII)	50
Bi(III)	250	Fluoride	5000
Cu(II)	50	Chloride	1000
Ag(I)	500	Bromide	3000
Au(III)	100	Iodide	4000
Cr(III)	100	Sulphate	15000
Fe(III)	1	Phosphate	10000
Mn(II)	6000	Nitrate	5000
Mn(VII)	100	Carbonate	1000
Ni(II)	500	Thiosulphate	6000
Cr(VI)	25	Oxalate	15000
Mo(VI)	5	Citrate	15000
W(VI)	25	Tartrate	15000
U(VI)	1000	Acetate	15000
Zr(IV)	10		

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